

now clear that the biotype in Bangladesh is not biotype 1 or 2, but is either 3 or 4. ■

List of BPH-resistant materials. BRRI, 1980.

Variety or line	Origin	Reaction ^a to BPH
ARC6650	India	HR
ARC10550		HR
ARC14529		HR
Sinna Sivappu	Thailand	HR
BR.593-1-1-5	Bangladesh	HR
BR593-46-8-2-1		HR
BR593-46-8-2		HR
BR593-46-8-2-4		HR
IR19661-347	IRRI	HR
IR19661-372	IRRI	HR
BG367-9	Sri Lanka	R
BG379-1		R
BG379-3		R
BR593-1-1-2	Bangladesh	R
BR593-1-1-3		R
BR593-48-8-2-5-3		R
IR13240-10-1	IRRI	R
IR13240-39-3		R
IR13240-1-B		R
IR13240-6-3		R
IR13240-10-1		R
IR13240-83-1		R
IR13426-19-2		R
IR13427-60-1		R
1314632-31-3		R
IR14632-272		R
IR19660-121		R
IR19660-189		R
IR19660-53		R
IR19660-161		R
IR19660-253		R
IR19660-192		R
IR19660-315		R
IR19661-13		R
IR19661-163		R
IR19661-364		R
Hondarwala	Sri Lanka	R

^a HR = highly resistant, R = resistant.

induced salinity.

Three hills were grown in each pot. One set of pots was irrigated with saline water (NaCl + CaCl₂ in 4 to 1 ratio), bringing soil EC_e to around 8 mmho/cm. Another set was irrigated with good quality water (EC-0.95 mmho/cm). CCC at 2,000 ppm and BA at 10 ppm were applied to pot sets as foliar sprays twice between primordial initiation and panicle emergence. Each treatment was replicated three times. Grain yield data indicate significant differences due to variety, salinity level, and growth regulator (see table). Under unsprayed saline conditions, Getu, with a 37.5% reduction from normal conditions, yielded more than Madhu with a 70.2% reduction from normal. However,

the extent of reduction varied under salinity in combination with growth regulator. In Getu, the yield was reduced further (72.4%) with BA but increased slightly (31.7%) with CCC. On the other hand, Madhu showed marked response to growth regulators under salinity, with a 55.3% yield reduction under BA and a 36.2% reduction under CCC. The apparent increase in yield could be attributed to increased grains per panicle and reduced spikelet sterility.

The results suggest that care be exercised in selecting varieties as well as growth regulators for improving productivity under saline situation. Getu, a salt-tolerant variety, did not better its performance when supplemented with growth regulators. ■

Effect of growth regulators and salinity on grain yield and associated characteristics of 2 rice varieties. Karnataka, India, 1974 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (g/pot)		Productive tillers (no./ pot)		Grain (no. panicle)		Spikelet sterility (%)		1,000-grain wt (g)	
	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu
Control normal	32.8	32.8	24.0	25.0	87	95	24.2	32.9	21.1	18.4
Control saline	19.9	9.5	20.7	16.0	69	61	34.6	35.8	17.5	15.3
BA normal	35.8	31.7	26.0	21.3	82	101	29.1	26.5	21.5	18.1
BA saline	8.8	13.6	16.3	17.3	41	74	46.2	31.0	15.3	14.1
CCC normal	27.8	31.4	18.7	22.0	83	100	28.9	30.1	21.5	18.2
CCC saline	22.0	28.9	19.3	18.7	73	83	29.3	32.3	20.0	14.1
Mean	23.0		20.4		79.1		31.7		17.9	
C.D. 5%										
Variety	1.4		ns		2.8		ns		0.5	
Salinity	1.4		1.5		2.8		1.6		0.5	
Growth regulator	1.7		ns		3.5		2.0		0.6	

^aBA = benzyl adenine. CCC = chloroethyl trimethyl ammonium chloride.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Varietal response to growth regulators under saline conditions

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A pot culture study during the 1974 wet season evaluated the effects of two growth regulators, 2-chloroethyl trimethyl ammonium chloride (CCC) and benzyl adenine (BA), on grain yields of rice varieties Getu and Madhu under

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Effect of seedling age on total plant elongation and internode elongation of deepwater rice

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Five recommended deepwater rice varieties were grown in wooden screening boxes (30 × 30 × 24 cm) for 10, 20, 30, and 40 days. Seedlings were then submerged in 100-cm deep water in con-

crete tanks for 7 days. The boxes were adjusted so that leaf tips were about 50 cm below water level.

The internodes of all varieties elongated as early as 20 days, but plant elongation occurred as early as 10 days. The percentage increase in plant elongation had no positive relation with the total length of internodes produced. Total plant elongation decreased with seedling age, but the number of internodes and their total length increased. The greatest plant elongation was observed in 10-day-old seedlings and the

Elongation ability of deepwater rice as affected by age of seedlings. BRRI, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Seedling age (d)	% increase in plant ht	Internode length (cm)	Internodes (no.)
<i>Habiganj Aman II</i>			
10	216	0	0
20	160.5	51.8	3.2
30	130.1	61.8	4.6
40	76.8	48.9	3.8
<i>Habiganj Aman III</i>			
10	177.8	0	0
20	112.8	43.6	2.5
30	134.2	63.0	4.6
40	134.2	49.9	3.6
<i>Habiganj Aman V</i>			
10	203.4	0	0
20	186.8	44.5	2.5
30	140.0	67.0	4.2
40	112.1	56.9	4.6
<i>Habiganj Aman VI</i>			
10	189.1	0	0
20	165.1	49.4	2.5
30	140.9	55.1	3.9
40	104.5	53.0	3.9
<i>Habiganj Aman VII</i>			
10	222.3	0	0
20	145.4	60.6	3.6
30	121.2	68.4	4.2
40	105.9	55.8	4.2

greatest internode length was recorded in 30-day-old seedlings.

It appears that total plant elongation ability and internode elongation ability

are different physiological phenomena, although equally important in varietal adaptation to flood-prone areas. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Effect of ash on the cold tolerance of rice at seedling stage

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In China, ash is applied either as basal or topdressing to seedbeds during the first cropping season before the onset of low temperature to increase cold tolerance and decrease cold injury at the seedling stage. The potassium-rich ash probably increases cold tolerance, and the dark color of the ash probably absorbs heat and raises water temperature. Two kinds of ash are used: from burnt stove firewood and from burnt straws or grasses with some soil added. Potassium (K₂O) content is 64%. Ash from burnt

straw has more nitrogen.

Three trials were conducted to evaluate whether application of ash could prevent or alleviate discoloration and death of rice seedlings subjected to cold water.

The first experiment tested two varieties — IR8, which is susceptible to low water temperature, and Fujisaka 5, which is resistant. Pulverized rice straw ash and ammonium sulfate were used in four treatments.

Ten rows of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 were sown alternately in each treatment tray. Ten days after soaking, the trays were placed in a circulating-cold-water (12° C) tank with water 2 cm above the soil surface.

The cold tolerance of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 measured by leaf discoloration is shown in the figure. The order of cold

Discoloration scores of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 seedlings grown with different combinations of ash and nitrogen, at different days after start of cold water treatment. IRRI, 1981.

tolerance in all treatments was: ash + N > N > ash > no ash, no N.

The succeeding two trials used only IR8 and added potash in two additional treatments. The order of cold tolerance for the six treatments was K + N > ash + N > K > ash > no ash, no N, no K > N. Leaf discoloration was observed after a day of cold water treatment in plants grown with no ash, no N, no K; with ash and with K. Plants grown in ash + N and K + N did not develop yellowing until 4 or 5 days after the start of the treatment.

Plant height increased despite low water temperature, with significantly higher percentage increases in K+N, and ash + N.

Application of ash or potassium mixed with nitrogen in the seedbed increased plant height, promoted growth, and slowed leaf discoloration, and thus increased cold tolerance during the seedling stage. The treatment is effective both with cold water-susceptible and tolerant varieties. ■